

To Study the Association of Serum Uric Acid an Independent Risk Factor in Acute Ischemic Stroke at DMCH, Laheriasarai, Bihar

Pankaj Mohan Shrivastava¹, U. C. Jha²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital (DMCH), Laheriasarai, Bihar

²Associate Professor and Head of Department, Department of Medicine, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital (DMCH), Laheriasarai, Bihar

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Corresponding author: Dr U. C. Jha

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Abstract

The aim was to investigate the relationship between acute ischemic non-embolic stroke and serum uric acid. 100 patients with the first acute ischemic stroke in their lifetime who were treated at DMCH, Laheriasarai, Bihar, were included. Within 24 hours of the stroke's beginning, blood samples were collected, and CT scans were performed. Blood samples were provided for 2D ECHO and biochemical analysis. The presence of additional risk factors such hypertension, diabetes, a poor lipid profile, smoking, and drunkenness was also assessed in the individuals. 68 of the 100 patients were men, and 32 were women. 49% of people had uric acid levels more than 8 mg/dl. 35% of them had diabetes, and 53% had hypertension. 24% of people smoked, and 21% drank alcohol. This study demonstrates a substantial correlation between elevated uric acid levels and a higher risk of developing an acute ischemic stroke. While treating high risk populations, lowering blood uric acid levels can be regarded one of the stroke prevention strategies.

Keywords: Serum Uric Acid, Acute Ischemic Stroke.

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Introduction

Cerebrovascular disorders undoubtedly rank top in prevalence and significance among all neurological conditions that affect adults. In a general hospital, this kind of neurological illnesses account for at least 50% of cases. The third most prevalent cause of death, behind cancer and heart disease, is a stroke. By promoting the lowering of risk factors, all doctors can contribute to the prevention of stroke [1]. A high socioeconomic load is also associated with stroke because of its increased morbidity and mortality [2]. Over 80% of all stroke occurrences are ischemic strokes. Primary preventive efforts may

benefit from early detection of those at risk [3]. In humans, uric acid is the most prevalent aqueous antioxidant and accounts for up to two thirds of plasma's total capacity to scavenge free radicals. It is very powerful at squelching hydroxyl, superoxide, and peroxy nitrite radicals, and by preventing lipid peroxidation, it may have a physiologically protective role.

Epidemiological studies have shown evidence that raised SUA levels may indicate a higher risk of cerebrovascular (CV) events, such as stroke [5-7].

Additionally, it has been demonstrated that therapeutic approaches with the potential to diminish SUA lessen CV disease morbidity and mortality [8]. In this way, SUA levels could be utilised as a simple serum test to identify at-risk individuals and treat them properly.

Insulin resistance and SUA have recently been linked [10]. It is unclear whether high SUA levels promote or protect against the development of CV disease or merely act as a passive or circumstantial marker of increased risk, despite the fact that high SUA levels have been identified as an important risk factor for stroke in unselected populations in a number of epidemiological studies[11].

Aim and Objectives

To study the association between serum uric acid and independent risk factors leading to acute ischemic stroke.

- Find the uric acid levels.
- Study independent risk factors
- Association of the risk factors and the disease

Results

Table 1: Age distribution among the study population

Age distribution in years	Frequency	Percentage
<40	7	7%
41-49	12	12%
50-59	27	27%
60-69	37	37%
70-79	15	15%
>80	2	2%
Total	100	100%

Table 1 reveals that 37% of respondents were in the age range of 60 to 69, 27% were in the range of 50 to 59, and 15% were in the range of 70 to 79.

Table 2: Gender distribution among the study population

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	68	68%
Female	32	32%

Material and Methods

In this prospective study, 100 patients with acute ischemic stroke who were admitted to the department of medicine at the Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital in Laheriasarai, Bihar, and who had a CT scan within 24 hours of the stroke's onset were included. The study took place between June 2022 and November 2022. Neuroimaging, laboratory testing, and a thorough clinical evaluation were all done to find patients who had acute ischemic strokes. All responders provided their freely given consent. Within 24 hours after the stroke's onset, blood samples were drawn and sent for biochemical analysis. Standard analyzers were used at our biochemical laboratory for the analysis. The presence of other risk factors was further assessed in the patients. Patients with a history of TIA or CVA, known cases of gout, chronic renal failure, cardiac conditions, haematological abnormalities, use of thiazide diuretics, chemotherapy, or uricosuric medications, as well as those whose CT scans revealed haemorrhage or other space-occupying lesions, were excluded from the study.

Table 2 displays the gender breakdown of the study population, with 68% of men and 32% of women.

Table 3: Uric acid level

Uric acid level	Frequency	Percentage
<2	25	25%
2-8	26	26%
>8	49	49%

Table 3 displays the uric acid levels, with the bulk of patients (49%), followed by 26% with levels between 2 and 8, and 25% with levels less than 2.

Table 4: Association of age and mean uric acid levels among the study population

Age distribution/uric acid	Mean	SD
<40	4.0	1.0
41-49	4.2	1.2
50-59	4.9	1.5
60-69	5.3	1.53
70-79	6.7	1.68
>80	6.3	2.1
P value	<0.05	

In Table 4, the study population's mean uric acid levels are correlated with age, with a p value of <0.05 indicating significance.

Table 5: Association between hypertension and uric acid levels

Uric acid level/hypertension	Present	Absent	Total
<2	5	20	25
2-8	14	12	26
>8	34	15	49
Total	53	47	100

Chi square = 16.22, df=2, p=0.0003

Table 5 illustrates the relationship between uric acid and hypertension, showing that 34 of the total 49 patients with uric acid levels greater than 8 mg/dl also had hypertension. 14 of the 26 patients with uric acid levels between 2 and 8 had hypertension. Five of the 25 patients with uric acid levels less than 2 mg/dl had hypertension. High significance was found in the chi square test with a p value <0.005.

Table 6: Association between uric acid and Diabetes Mellitus

Uric acid level/Mellitus	Present	Absent	Total
<2	3	22	25
2-8	10	16	26
>8	22	27	49
Total	35	65	100

Table 6 illustrates the relationship between uric acid and diabetes mellitus, showing that 22 of the total 49 individuals with uric acid levels greater than 8 mg/dl also had the disease. Ten of the 26 patients with uric acid levels between 2 and 8 had diabetes.

Three of the 25 patients with uric acid levels less than 2 mg/dl had diabetes. Chi square test, significance was found, $p < 0.01$.

Discussion

In the current study, it was found that 37% of respondents were between the ages of 60 and 69, 27% were between the ages of 50 and 59, and 15% were between the ages of 70 and 79. 25% of the patients in this study are above 65 years old, with 12 men and 13 women. Similar results were observed in the current investigation. According to Millinois *et al.* [9], regardless of the presence of concurrent metabolic disturbances, SUA is linked to an elevated risk for acute ischaemic/non-embolic stroke in aged patients. The current study demonstrates the relationship between uric acid and hypertension. Of the 49 patients with uric acid levels greater than 8 mg/dl, 34 individuals also had hypertension. Out of 26 patients having uric acid in range of 2 to 8, 14 patients were having hypertension.

Out of 25 having uric acid level less than 2 mg/dl, 5 patients were having hypertension. Tushar Patil *et al* [12] and Millinois *et al.* [9]; shows similar results.

The population of the current study has DM, with 35% of respondents reporting having it. In this study, there is a significant correlation between SUA and DM, with a mean SUA level of 5.98 mg/dl in diabetics and 4.88 mg/dl in non-diabetics. The majority of the 35 individuals in the current study's link between uric acid and diabetes mellitus (DM) study had DM, demonstrating that as blood uric acid levels rose, so did the prevalence of stroke in DM patients. There was a

statistically significant difference in SUA levels in diabetes and nondiabetic patients in Tushar Patil *et al* study [12]. The DM and SUA both had similar importance in the current investigation. The current study demonstrated that the radiological findings on CT scan revealed that the majority of patients, or 30%, were affected in the MCA territory, followed by 26% in the PCA territory, then 18% in the thalamus, then 10% in the internal capsule, then 7% in the caudate nucleus, then 5% in the corona radiata, then 3% in the centrum semi ovale, and finally only 1% in the hemisphere. According to a study by Chamorro A *et al.* [13], uric acid also had an adverse relationship with neurological impairment at the time of admission ($P=0.001$) and the extent of the final infarction on CT/MRI ($P=0.01$).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates a clear correlation between greater SUA and an increased risk of developing an acute ischemic stroke. When treating aged people and diabetics, the link between high SUA and ischemic stroke may need to be taken into account.

One of the risk factors for acute ischemic stroke and its related metabolic illnesses, such as hypertension and diabetes, is elevated SUA.

If you are treating a high-risk group, lowering the SUA level might be thought of as one of your preventative stroke treatment options. To determine whether lowering SUA levels with dietary changes, lifestyle changes, and medication can ultimately minimise the risk of ischemic stroke, more research is needed.

References

1. Adam and Victor's principles of Neurology – 8th edition; Chapter 34; 660-669.
2. Bonita R. Epidemiology of stroke. Lancet, 1992; 339: 342–4.

3. Buckley BM. Healthy ageing: ageing safely. *Eur Heart J*, 2001; (3): N6– 10.
4. Squadrito GL, Cueto R, Splenser AE, Valavanidis A, Zhang H, Uppu RM, *et al.* Reaction of uric acid with peroxynitrite and implications for the mechanism of neuroprotection by uric acid. *Arch Biochem Biophys* 2000; 376: 333– 337.
5. Fang J, Alderman MH; Serum uric acid and cardiovascular mortality. The NHANES I epidemiologic follow-up study, 1971–1992. *JAMA*, 2000; 283: 2404–10.
6. Lehto S, Niskanen L, Ronnema T, Laasko M. Serum uric acid is a strong predictor of stroke in patients with non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. *Stroke*, 1998; 29: 635–9.
7. Weir CJ, Muir SW, Walters MR, Lees KR. Serum urate as an independent predictor of poor outcome and future vascular events after acute stroke. *Stroke*, 2003; 34: 1951–6.
8. Hoiegggen A, Alderman MH, Kjeldsen SE, Julius S, Devereux RB, De Faire U. *et al.* LIFE Study Group. The impact of serum uric acid on cardiovascular outcomes in the LIFE study. *Kidney Int*, 2004; 65(3): 1041–9.
9. Milionis HJ, Kalantzi KJ, Goudevenos JA, Seferiadis K, Mikhailidis DP, Elisaf MS. Serum uric acid levels and risk for acute ischaemic nonembolic stroke in elderly subjects. *J Intern Med*, 2005; 258: 435–441.
10. Li, Changgui, Ming-Chia Hsieh, Shun-Jen Chang. Metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and hyperuricemia. *Current opinion in rheumatology*, 2013; 25(2): 210-216.
11. Mehrpour M, Khuzan M, Najimi N, Motamed M.R, Fereshtehnejad S.M. Serum uric acid level in acute stroke patients. *Medical journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 2012; 26(2): 66-72.
12. Patil TB, Pasari AS, Sargar KM, Shegokar VE, Bansod YV, Patil MB. Serum Uric Acid Levels in Acute Ischemic Stroke: A Study of 100 Patients. *Journal of Neurology Research*, 2011; 1(5):193-200.
13. Chamorro A, Obach V, Cervera A, Revilla M, Deulofeu R, Aponte JH. Prognostic significance of uric acid serum concentration in patients with acute ischemic stroke. *Stroke*, 2002; 33(4):1048-1052.